

Etymological, Semantic, and Cognitive Evolution of Virtuality: A Synchronic and Diachronic Analysis

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Abstract: The article investigates the multifaceted nature of virtuality through synchronic and diachronic approaches. It focuses on the etymology, semantic evolution, and cognitive transformation of the concept of virtuality, starting with its ancient roots in Indo-European languages and tracking its development through philosophical thought, medieval scholasticism, and the emergence of scientific terminology in the Renaissance. By examining key terms such as *vrt*, *virt*, *virtus*, and *virtuality*, the paper explores how these words evolved from indicating potentiality and possibility to embodying concepts of force, power, and later, virtual reality. The study includes the ideas of notable philosophers like Patanjali, Aristotle, Cicero, Thomas Aquinas, and Galileo, shedding light on the linguistic and conceptual shifts that shaped modern understandings of virtuality. Through this diachronic lens, the article illustrates how the conceptualization of virtuality has been enriched over millennia, culminating in its current scientific and philosophical significance.

Keywords: virtuality, synchronic analysis, cognitive transformation, potentiality, renaissance science, virtual reality.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of virtuality, with its diverse implications and meanings, has undergone significant transformation over time. This paper delves into the etymological, semantic, and cognitive aspects of virtuality, employing both synchronic and diachronic approaches to explore its evolution. By analyzing the development of virtualistic terms, concepts, and categories across various periods, this study provides insights into the dynamic nature of virtuality. The synchronic approach allows for an exploration of the views and meanings attributed to virtuality at a specific moment in history, with a particular focus on the 20th century, when virtualistic concepts gained prominence in philosophical and scientific discourse.

In contrast, the diachronic approach traces the historical evolution of these concepts, examining how terms related to virtuality have transformed across different eras. Through this lens, we investigate the origins of words such as *vrt*, *virt*, and *Virtus*, which form the linguistic and semantic foundation of virtuality. These words, stemming from the ancient Indo-European linguistic roots, carried meanings of change, force, and potentiality that gradually morphed into the modern understandings of virtuality. By examining philosophical texts from figures such as Patanjali, Aristotle, Cicero, and later medieval thinkers like Thomas Aquinas, we see how these terms have shaped the intellectual landscape over millennia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Furthermore, the study highlights the transition from the ancient and medieval uses of these words, linked to virtue, power, and potential, to the more recent interpretations in fields like physics and philosophy, where virtuality has become synonymous with concepts of possibility and potentiality. The research also touches upon the crucial role of the Renaissance and the 19th century, during which the term virtuality evolved to represent scientific concepts in mechanics, probability, and, ultimately, virtual reality.

Through the intersection of linguistics, philosophy, and cognitive science, this paper offers a comprehensive examination of the long-standing conceptual journey of virtuality. By tracing its etymological roots, semantic shifts, and cognitive transformations, it provides a deeper understanding of the multifaceted nature of virtuality and its significance in both historical and contemporary contexts.

Analysis of polysemantic aspects of virtuality, including etymological, semantic and cognitive transformations occurring in it, based on synchronic and diachronic approaches makes it possible to obtain certain heuristic results. In a study based on the synchronic approach, views on the problem of virtuality, the content of virtualistic terms, concepts and categories within a certain period or time are considered. In this case, for example, virtualistic views and concepts developed in the 20th century become the subject of philosophical and methodological reflection and scientific and theoretical analysis. In a study based on the principles of the diachronic approach (evolutionary epistemological analysis, polymorphic cognitivism, historicism, temporal comparative analysis and other principles), the evolution of virtualistic terms and cognitive structures arising over a certain period of time is studied. In the framework of our research, we will examine the etymological semantics of the words "vrt", "virt", "Virtus", which lie in the linguosemantic basis of the concept of "virtuality", the formation of the concept of "virtus" and related words and ideas about them in the languages of different peoples. The word Core f'El (in comparative diachronic linguistics as a word denoting a single-base cognate), which existed in the ancient Indo-European group of languages, meant "vrt" change, subsequent force, phenomenon [1]. According to another etymological approach, the root of the word "virtus" goes back to the word "wih-Ro", belonging to the primitive Indo-European language, meaning man, person [2]. It is noteworthy that this word had a linguosemantic potential, a tendency to form various words and terms in other languages, denoting the transition from possibility to reality in perspective. Indeed, over the centuries, this linguistic, that is, terminological tendency became an etymological reality in the works of Patanjali, Aristotle, Cicero, Al-Kindi, Thomas Aquinas, Nicholas of Kusan and other thinkers, creating various virtualistic words and expressions. With this etymological and linguosemantic tradition in mind, researchers claim that the idea of virtuality has existed for three thousand years [3].

3. METHODOLOGY & EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

The Indian philosopher Patanjali, who lived in the second century BC, in his "Yoga Sutra" uses the word "Vritti" for designations of changes in the mind. According to the interpretation given by the philosopher, "Vritti" refers to fluctuations of the mind, in particular to the transition from one mental functional state to another of 5 types. These are: pramana - correct knowledge, reflecting reality as it is; viparyaya - a state (moment) when the mind erroneously makes an incorrect judgment, which can later be replaced by correct knowledge; vikalpa - imagination, in which words have no direct relation to reality; nidra - sleep. Patanjali writes: "sleep is a Vritti that takes on the feeling of emptiness" [4]; Smriti are words stored in memory. According to the description given by the thinker, each functional type of mind has the ability to move to another functional type (state), that is, there is a virtual thought. In this regard, the thoughts of the philosopher Patanjali can be considered as an early expression of the idea of virtuality.

The etymological innovation (the adjective innovating), associated with the idea of virtuality, belongs to Aristotle. The Thinker reflected on the connection between form and matter, using the words "movement towards matter", "energy", "charging force"; "the possibility that preserves this force" - "Dynamics"; "the goal that turns possibility into reality" - "result" - "entelechy". It can be said that in this way Aristotle introduced into philosophical thought terms of a fundamentally virtualistic nature, possessing a conceptual content that was new for that time. Medieval scholastics borrowed the word "Dynamis", given in the Thinker's "Metaphysics" (in an attempt to express the meanings of possibility, ability, preserved in this word), into the Latin term "virtus". The etymological root of the word "virtualis", borrowed from the Romance language, goes back to the Latin word "virtus". The correct part of this word was "vir", which meant a man. The word "Virtus", in turn, is a Roman term meaning bravery, strength, tenacity, Courage, Goodness, Glory, Nobility, moral perfection and other meanings inherent in people, qualities by which one judges a person. The word "virtue" first appears in a magnanimous, courageous, noble sense in the book of Marcus Tullius Cicero "On the Nature of the Gods". In Medieval Europe, in the context of interpreting the ideas of Plato and Aristotle in Latin in accordance with Christian teaching, the word "virtus" acquired a bilingual meaning. Firstly, the meanings of the word "virtus" expressed in the language of the ancient Romans were preserved. Secondly, the scholastic philosophers defined the concepts of strength, ability, potentiality expressed by the Thinker in Greek words in the interpretation of ontological ideas given in Aristotelian metaphysics in Latin, with the word "virtus". The bilingual status of the word "virtus" was preserved almost until the 19th century. At the same time, it should be noted that in medieval scholastic philosophy the word "virtue" was given a new meaning. Interpreting the creation of the Universe in the 4th century, Basil the Great, an outstanding priest of Byzantine Christianity, tried to explain the connection between reality in a potential state and existing reality using the term "virtuality" [5]. The theological heart characterizes the essence of the psyche, including the fact that the psyche is in different positions in relation to the body, with the word "virtue". In European scholastic philosophy of the 13th century, the term "virtuality" received serious ontological and cognitive content-meaning. For example, Duns Scotus introduced the new term "virtualism" for that time in an attempt to clarify the formulation of the virtualist ideas of Aristotle and Thomas Aquinas. Thomas Aquinas uses the word "virtus" when describing the hierarchy of the human psyche, using the lower forms as the basis of thinking - perception, growth (vegetative), soul (Latin: animus), comes to the idea that it exists in a virtual form [6].

4. RESULTS

In the Renaissance, the idea of virtuality and the terms that represent it were used to solve problems related to the foundations of mechanics. It can be said that the term "virtus" (by adding other words to the root word) was first used in the field of natural science, in particular in the study of virtual states of force and virtual change of place, where material points in mechanics are a condition for ensuring the dynamic stability of the system [7]. Outstanding scientists of this period (G. Galileo, G. Ubaldi, I. Bernoulli) introduced new vitalistic terms - "virtus movertis", "virtual", giving the word "virtus" the meaning of possibility, potentiality and, thus, enriching the thesaurus (etymological resource) of the language of natural sciences. The etymological and semantic innovations of these scientists, realized in connection with the idea of virtuality, were continued in the new, quite recent times.

The etymological, lexical and cognitive renewal of the term "virtuality" took place in the 19th century. The dictionary published by the French Academy in 1878 lists 3 lexical meanings of the word "virtuality": 1. Virtuality, i.e. in the sense of possibility, potentiality; 2. Unactualized power, meaning Power in content; 3. In the sense of a probabilistic method, which acts as a grammatical dialect, located in a position opposite to reality. Thanks to this, the word "virtuality" received the status of a scientific term and concept included in the encyclopedic dictionary. In conclusion, in the course of the transition from the centuries-old concept of

"virtus" to the concept of "virtual reality", a co-evolutionary progress and clarification between the idea of virtuality and its language (the shell of virtualistic terms) took place, and the evolutionary epistemological transformation and renewal of this diachronic character led to the structure of the virtualistic scientific direction and the explanatory dictionary of this direction. This served as a serious impetus for the development of mutually alternative interpretations and approaches to the idea of virtuality in many respects. The linguosemantic and theoretical-conceptual evolution of the idea of virtuality, which has occurred from antiquity to the present day, confirms this.

The analysis of the polysemantic aspects of virtuality, including its etymological, semantic, and cognitive transformations, has revealed the profound evolution of this concept over millennia. By employing both synchronic and diachronic approaches, this study has highlighted the diverse meanings of virtuality and traced its development from ancient linguistic and philosophical traditions to contemporary scientific discourses.

The synchronic approach, focusing on specific periods such as the 20th century, has provided valuable insights into the modern understanding of virtuality, especially as it gained philosophical and scientific importance. The diachronic perspective, on the other hand, has illuminated the gradual evolution of virtualistic terms, concepts, and ideas, showing how the ancient roots of words like *vrt*, *virt*, and *Virtus* laid the foundation for the concept of virtuality. From early usages in the works of Patanjali, Aristotle, and Cicero, to the medieval scholastics and Renaissance thinkers, the term "virtus" and its derivatives evolved in response to new intellectual challenges, eventually shaping the modern understanding of virtuality.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Notably, the transition from metaphysical and theological interpretations of potentiality to its use in fields like mechanics and natural sciences in the Renaissance, and the subsequent lexicon expansions in the 19th century, demonstrate the dynamic and adaptive nature of the concept. By the 19th century, the term "virtuality" had gained widespread academic recognition, embodying meanings of potentiality, unactualized power, and probabilistic reasoning, further solidifying its status as a key scientific term.

Ultimately, the evolution of virtuality, as examined through its etymology, semantics, and cognitive transformations, underscores the interplay between language, thought, and knowledge. This co-evolutionary process has not only expanded the conceptual boundaries of virtuality but has also spurred alternative interpretations and approaches to the idea, which continue to inform contemporary discussions in various academic and scientific domains. Thus, the linguosemantic and theoretical-conceptual evolution of virtuality serves as a testament to the enduring relevance and adaptability of this fundamental concept throughout history.

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